

AI-Enhanced Seamless Handover in Wi-Fi Networks with Multi-Link Management

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Abstract—This work presents an innovative Multi-Parameter Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based decision algorithm, designed to optimize handovers in Wi-Fi networks supporting Multi-Link Operation (MLO). The algorithm leverages a combination of Neural Networks (NN), integrating a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) NN with a Classification NN. The former predicts key performance indicators, which are then used by the latter to determine the optimal connection between a Wi-Fi Station and available Access Points. Our approach, compared to traditional distance-based handovers, effectively improves connectivity in more complex and realistic curvilinear trajectories, especially in scenarios with interference.

Index Terms—AI, Wi-Fi, Handover, Multi-Link Operation, Long-Short-Term Memory, Classification Neural Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in developing efficient strategies to manage handovers, often initiated by user mobility within large areas like industrial manufacturing sites or smart cities [1]. Specifically, in the context of IEEE 802.11 (Wi-Fi) networks, horizontal handover ensures smooth traffic transition between Stations (STAs) and Access Points (APs), for continuous and reliable wireless connections [2].

In this scenario, most handover optimization strategies rely on a single metric, e.g., distance between STA and APs or Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). However, due to the complexity of mobility environments influenced by numerous other metrics like latency, Signal-To-Noise Ratio (SNR), interference, and throughput across multiple links, we propose the Multi-Parameter Artificial Intelligence-based Decision (MPAID) algorithm, which better captures connection states and outperforms traditional distance-based methods.

The Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Network (NN) of the MPAID uses distance of STAs from each AP, their coordinates, speed, and direction of movement to forecast predictive metrics (latency, SNR, and RSSI for each AP) for future time intervals. These predictions serve as inputs to the Classification NN, which decides the optimal AP to connect to the STA. In addition, we enhance handovers by exploiting the

Multi-Link Operation (MLO) feature of the IEEE 802.11be (Wi-Fi 7) standard, which enables wireless devices, known as Multi-Link Devices (MLDs), to operate on multiple links simultaneously, minimizing interruptions during handover and improving throughput and reliability [3]–[6].

Finally, we compare scenarios with and without two additional interfering STAs, highlighting the advantages of MPAID in managing the horizontal handover decision process, utilizing multiple metrics to enhance the selection of APs for improved connectivity and reliability, especially in scenarios with interference.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews handover optimization methods; Section 3 details our novel AI-based approach; Section 4 outlines the experimental setup; Section 5 shows the results compared to a baseline; Section 6 summarizes the paper and suggests future work.

II. BACKGROUND AND STATE-OF-THE-ART

According to the IEEE 802.11 standard, the handover process involves two main steps [7]:

- 1) Discovery: The STA searches for potential APs to connect with using the *scan* function of the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer, which involves listening for beacon messages on designated channels. Based on the RSSI, the STA prioritizes a list of APs. Scanning can be either passive, where the STA only listens to beacon frames, or active, where the STA also sends probe requests and receives responses from APs.
- 2) Reauthentication: Authentication and re-association with the new AP are performed, by transferring credentials and other state information from the previous AP.

Handover optimization decisions are often based on a single metric, whereas NNs offer a promising alternative by enabling the simultaneous consideration of multiple metrics. NNs, with advanced predictive capabilities and complex data processing, can enhance handover efficiency, optimizing decision-making and overall connection quality, thus becoming increasingly relevant across different areas. For example, in autonomous vehicles, NNs are crucial for interpreting sensor data from cameras, Light Detection And Ranging (LiDAR) and radar to make informed decisions about navigation, obstacle avoidance, and safety [8], [9]. In industrial automation, they improve predictive maintenance, operational optimization, and quality

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control, e.g., as shown in [10] where an AI algorithm is presented to monitor and predict gas imbalances in distribution systems. NNs are also used for security, as proposed in [11], where an algorithm that combines Convolutional NN (CNN) and LSTM is used to improve industrial system defenses against Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks. In healthcare NNs are used to analyze medical images or predict health status as in [12], where LSTM is employed to increase performance and accuracy in action recognition tasks using sensor data from gyroscopes and accelerometers.

In the field of communication, diverse NN-based approaches have been proposed to optimize handover procedures. In [13], a cloud-based architecture is proposed to deploy a more efficient split of functionalities in a Wi-Fi network, enabling a more robust and faster handover procedure. In [14], a Gittins index-based framework is introduced to find an optimal stop of fractional Markovian multi-objective selections procedures, often employed in handover decisions. In [15], a novel CNN structure is compared with LSTM structures and measured Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) values are used to determine whether to perform or not a handover. In [16], a more concrete method to predict the probability of upcoming handovers in Wi-Fi networks is proposed, leveraging a ML approach to monitor RSSI patterns over time. In [17], a multi-step time-series prediction approach with a random forest algorithm is utilized to address handover prediction, reducing unnecessary handovers by 60% compared to the RSS method. In [18], an anticipation-based handover solution using a Kalman filter is introduced, allowing proactive scanning and handover execution when better APs are available; however, this approach is limited by its reliance on RSSI alone. Similarly, authors in [19] propose the selection of the closest AP through a positioning process that prioritizes the AP with the shortest geometric distance to the STA; although straightforward, this method overlooks factors like network load, RSSI, or latency. Also authors in [20] neglect other key metrics, focusing only on maximizing throughput considering the AP load and the available bandwidth. Similarly in [21] the handover decision is based only on the distance between the STA and the APs. Handover challenges have recently attracted interest in mixed terrestrial-satellite networks, where efficient management across diverse access networks is particularly difficult. For instance, authors in [22] integrate a multi-criteria based vertical handover technique for efficient handover among Wi-Fi, cellular and satellite networks. Finally, a very recent survey of handover optimization approaches in Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) can be found in [23].

Other works focus on enhancing Wi-Fi features to ensure reliable operations in noisy industrial environments. Authors in [24] extend the Wi-Fi 802.11CB standard and demonstrate how multi-radio redundancy capabilities can achieve zero-delay roaming for mobile robots. Authors in [25] exploit Digital Twins (DTs) to moving STAs in Wi-Fi supporting MLO to perform seamless roaming between APs. Authors in [26] look at the MLO feature from the energy consumption point of view, proposing a framework to reduce the overall

system energy budget. Authors in [27] propose a low-cost experimental platform to learn how to optimize Wi-Fi features in industrial environments. Finally, authors in [28] introduce an LSTM-based model that focuses only on predicting the RSRP metric.

It is noteworthy that this work is based on [29] and that authors in [30] use a comparable ML algorithm in a more simplified framework. Specifically, on the one hand their approach does not incorporate the MLO feature and is limited to a configuration that involves a single STA and two APs; on the other hand they compare the outcomes of two methodologies, i.e., a Classification NN and a decision rule, applied in the algorithm after the LSTM NN. Conversely, MPAID is designed to operate in a more advanced scenario where Wi-Fi 7 with the MLO feature is enabled, focusing solely on the Classification NN, and taking into consideration MLD devices and interference. This distinction underscores the enhanced complexity and applicability of our approach in optimizing network performance under more realistic conditions. Unlike previous methods that use a single metric, overlooking key factors affecting wireless links quality and reliability, our approach extends LSTM to predict multiple Key Performance Indicators, (KPIs), e.g., latency, SNR, and RSSI, thus offering advantages that collectively enhance connection quality in a noisy network using WiFi 7 with the MLO capability enabled.

III. THE MPAID ALGORITHM

Our MPAID algorithm employs a sequential NN framework, integrating an LSTM NN with a subsequent Classification NN, as shown in Fig. 1. It leverages predictive capabilities of the LSTM to estimate KPIs, which are then processed by the Classification NN to enable proactive handover decisions, assisting the MLD STA in predicting the best target MLD AP.

Fig. 2 provides a schematic overview of this process, while the pseudocode of the novel algorithm is detailed in Alg. 1.

Fig. 1: MPAID algorithm logic.

A task queue system supports concurrent task execution using a thread-safe queue to manage tasks in a multi-threaded scenario. It involves a continuous data collection process that captures data every 10 ms. Once 10 sequences of data are collected, the algorithm proceeds with pre-processing the data, applies the LSTM model to such pre-processed data, and calls

Fig. 2: Numbered boxes depict the MPAID sequential data flow through the processing pipeline. Blue-bordered ones indicate the coordination and distribution of tasks from the task queue to relevant components, red-bordered ones the execution and management of tasks by the management system.

the Classification NN to the predictions provided by the LSTM model. Hence, network flow adjustments are made based on the output of the Classification NN. Specifically, network flow management involves disabling all three links and MAC layers from the MLD STA to the previous MLD AP and enabling the corresponding ones to the new MLD AP. Additionally, all packets queued at the MAC layer or the PHY layer for the previous MLD AP are deleted to ensure seamless transition and prevent data congestion, while the network flow to the new MLD AP is started. Monitoring and logging tasks are integral to track system performance and record key data for analysis. Hence, while task management is overseen by a dedicated thread that continuously monitors the task queue, ensuring controlled task execution, preventing race conditions, and maintaining thread safety, the task enqueueing mechanism locks the queue, adds tasks, and alerts the processing thread, facilitating task handling and preserving system responsiveness. To demonstrate the efficiency of the MPAID algorithm, we utilize several key metrics: latency, packet delivery ratio (PDR), i.e., the ratio of packets received to packets sent, and the number of handovers occurred between the MLD and APs. In detail, such metrics are compared against a baseline, i.e., the widely used distance-based algorithm. The setups studied are without and with interference to prove the effectiveness of the algorithm in a more realistic scenario.

Algorithm 1 MPAID algorithm

- 1: Simulation starts \rightarrow set "System in operation"
 - 2: **Data Collection:**
 - 3: Schedule data collection every 10 ms
 - 4: **while** System in operation **do**
 - 5: Collect data: (x, y) STA position, (v_x, v_y) velocities
 - 6: **if** 10 sequences of values are collected **then**
 - 7: Add a data processing task to the queue
 - 8: **end if**
 - 9: **end while**
 - 10: **Data Processing:**
 - 11: **while** A data processing task is in the queue **do**
 - 12: Compute distances between STA and each AP, compute velocity and direction of movement of the STA
 - 13: Organize the data into the 6 input features required by the LSTM model
 - 14: Normalize the pre-processed data
 - 15: **end while**
 - 16: **LSTM Model Prediction:**
 - 17: Apply the LSTM model to predict future KPIs
 - 18: **Post Processing with Classification NN:**
 - 19: Use the Classification NN to determine the optimal AP for connection
 - 20: **if** The predicted AP differs from the current AP **then**
 - 21: Add a handover task to the queue
 - 22: **end if**
 - 23: **Network Flow Management:**
 - 24: **if** A handover task is present in the queue **then**
 - 25: Execute the handover task
 - 26: Disable the 3 links to the previous AP
 - 27: Enable the 3 links to the new AP
 - 28: Initiate network flow to the new AP
 - 29: **end if**
-

A. Development and Training of the LSTM model

The simulation setup involves the STA moving within a two-dimensional space, following both linear and curvilinear paths, i.e., circular, arc, elliptical, and spiral paths, with variations in velocity and starting position to develop a robust NN model. The random generation of initial positions and velocities ensures that the STA covers an area of 2500 m².

To collect complete data, each simulation is performed twice using the distance-based approach: initially connecting the mobile MLD STA to the nearest MLD AP, then to the furthest one. Data are collected from the last 10 time instants, each 10 ms apart, capturing the position (x_{STA}, y_{STA}) and velocity (v_x, v_y) of the mobile MLD STA. Knowing the positions of the MLD APs, the controller pre-processes the data for the LSTM model by calculating the distances from each MLD AP, as well as the speed and direction of the mobile MLD STA. Hence, the LSTM model uses six input features: the coordinates of the mobile MLD STA (x_{STA}, y_{STA}) , its speed $v = \sqrt{v_x^2 + v_y^2}$, direction $\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{v_y}{v_x}\right)$, and distances to each AP, $d_{STA,AP1}$ and $d_{STA,AP2}$, calculated

as $\sqrt{(x_{STA} - x_{AP_i})^2 + (y_{STA} - y_{AP_i})^2}$ for $i \in 1, 2$.

Data is organized to provide a look-back of 10 time steps, with KPIs such as latency, SNR, and RSSI for each AP computed as mean values at 10 ms intervals. Latency is measured as the end-to-end (E2E) STA to AP latency; RSSI, in dBm, is derived using the free space path loss model, considering transmitted powers and positions; SNR is calculated as the difference between received signal power and thermal noise power density. The dataset, compiled from all simulation runs, is normalized using `StandardScaler`, scaling each feature individually. It is structured to ensure separate batch processing for each simulation, preventing data mixing and allowing independent learning. The data set is divided into training, validation, and test sets in a 60 : 20 : 20 ratio. The LSTM model predicts the KPIs for each AP over an horizon of 300 ms, balancing accuracy and response time using 10 past intervals to forecast the next 30. The architecture features two layers with a hidden size of 128, processing sequences through fully connected layers with ReLU activation functions. The final output layer predicts KPIs, trained using a masked mean square error (MSE) loss function to handle missing or invalid data. Hyperparameters are initially set based on prior research and then refined through iterative tuning guided by performance metrics like prediction accuracy and loss evaluation. This empirical method aids in achieving convergence to a local minimum, as confirmed by simulation results.

B. Development and Training of the Classification NN

To enable effective AP selection using predicted KPIs, the Classification NN processes sequences from the LSTM model, assigning them to one of two classes that correspond to AP1 or AP2, thus determining the optimal AP for STA connection. The NN is trained using a dataset that includes KPI values for each AP, i.e., latency, SNR, and RSSI, which were previously used as target features for the LSTM model.

The input to the Classification NN consists of sequences of these 6 predicted features, each spanning 30 time steps, consistent with the prediction horizon of the LSTM model. Each feature is standardized using `StandardScaler`, ensuring uniform scaling across the dataset. This approach matches the normalization applied during LSTM training, eliminating the need to re-normalize predicted KPIs before they are fed into the classification network. The classification labels are derived from a scoring system calculated for each AP within a sequence window. The score is defined as the sum of SNR and RSSI, adjusted by latency. Specifically, a sequence of network measurements for AP $i \in 1, 2$ on a window length T , that is, $T = 30$, is represented as:

$$s_i = \left\{ \left(\text{SNR}_i^{(t)}, \text{RSSI}_i^{(t)}, \text{lat}_i^{(t)} \right) \right\}_{t=1}^T$$

where $t \in 1, 2, \dots, T$ indicates discrete time steps within the window, capturing the SNR, RSSI and latency values observed for AP i at each time step t . The scoring function \mathcal{S}_i for each AP over the sequence is defined as:

$$\mathcal{S}_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\text{SNR}_i^{(t)} + \text{RSSI}_i^{(t)} - \text{lat}_i^{(t)} \right)$$

So that, the classification label $y \in 0, 1$ is assigned based on the AP with the highest score \mathcal{S}_i :

$$y = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \mathcal{S}_1 > \mathcal{S}_2 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Thus, the label is assigned to the AP with the highest average score across the sequence, allowing the model to learn to select the AP with the best expected performance over the given time window. The dataset is split into training, validation, and test sets in a 60 : 20 : 20 ratio. The Classification NN architecture includes three fully connected layers, with ReLU activations between layers and dropout applied after each hidden layer for regularization. The model is optimized using the Adam optimizer and employs cross-entropy loss as the objective function. Hyperparameters are set empirically, following the approach used for the LSTM model.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL CONFIGURATION

MPAID is implemented and validated in the ns3 network simulator, modeling the functional parameters and communication behaviors of the MLD STA and MLD APs. This network comprises a MLD STA, which interacts with two stationary MLD APs (AP1 and AP2), a server, and a remote control unit responsible for real-time network optimization. To increase the realism of the scenario and introduce network interference, two additional static MLD STAs, i.e., STA1 and STA2, are incorporated to facilitate MLO. The network configuration used is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: ns3 network configuration and MLD internal structure.

Two different scenarios are considered: 1) STA1 and STA2 are not present; 2) STA1 and STA2 are present. In this configuration, the STAs act as a data source, continuously transmitting frames to the connected AP, using Wi-Fi 7 with MLO, allowing transmissions across 3 frequency bands, each with center frequencies of 2.4GHz, 5GHz, and 6GHz. The frames received by the APs are then sent to the server, which acts only as receiver, via Ethernet connections. Hence, the traffic is unidirectional, from the STA to the server. In the

first scenario, despite MLO being supported, the mobile STA connects only to one AP at the time, and the choice to which AP the STA has to connect to is provided by the off-board controller, which is responsible for evaluating handovers and determining the optimal AP for the STA through the proposed optimized approach. Instead in the second scenario, to add interference in the network and to make it more realistic, two additional static STAs are added, each communicating with one AP and maintaining the connection with them during all the simulation. In such case, the two additional STAs send frames using Variable Bit Rate (VBR).

Taking into account this architecture, the network configuration parameters are as follows: the transmission power is set to 17 dBm for MLD STAs and 20 dBm for the MLD APs. Each node is equipped with two antennas for transmitting and receiving. The maximum transmission opportunity (TXOP) duration for both MLD APs and MLD STA is configured to be 5600 ms. To maintain network synchronization and inform the mobile MLD STA of the presence and capabilities of MLD APs, the interval between consecutive beacon transmissions is set to 102.4 ms and the network load at 10 Mbps.

Mobility is introduced only through the mobile MLD STA, which follows linear or curvilinear trajectories, while AP1 and AP2 remain fixed at coordinates (15, 15) and (15, 35), respectively, in a two-dimensional space free from obstacles. In the second scenario, 2 stationary MLD STAs are introduced, STA1 located at (5, 15) and STA2 at (30, 20). Each STA establishes communication with the nearest AP, with STA1 connecting to AP1 and STA2 to AP2.

V. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

The accuracy of the predictions and the generalization ability of the trained LSTM model are rigorously evaluated to confirm their effectiveness. Fig. 4 shows the training and validation loss curves, highlighting model convergence and marking the stage at which the model reliably generalizes to unseen data. Further insights into the ability of the model to predict KPIs, for both linear and curvilinear trajectories, are presented in Fig. 5, where the measured KPIs are shown in blue and the predicted ones in orange. A detailed examination of the figure reveals slight inconsistencies in some KPI values, suggesting potential areas for improvement in future studies. By embedding real-world parameters into the model, variations can be reduced, leading to more accurate KPI predictions.

The training and validation losses of the Classification NN are shown in Fig. 6 while, in Fig. 7, the associate confusion matrix is depicted. This matrix highlights the discrepancies between the ground truth and the predicted labels, the former determined using the distance-based method. The confusion matrix demonstrates the precision of the proposed Classification NN, which reaches 99.93%, indicating the robustness of the model in accurately classifying the data.

To determine the performance of the proposed optimized approach, a comparative study is carried out evaluating the MPAID algorithm against a baseline method that relies solely on distance for handover decisions. To ensure a comprehensive

Fig. 4: Train and Validation losses of the LSTM NN.

analysis, 100 test simulations are conducted for each scenario. These simulations involve the mobile MLD STA starting from various initial positions and moving at different speeds, creating linear and curvilinear paths.

Table I compares the average performance metrics of MPAID with those of the traditional distance-based method, considering scenarios with and without two additional static MLD STAs, in linear and curvilinear trajectories. The metrics evaluated include average latency, latency standard deviation, average number of handovers, and packet delivery ratio (PDR), i.e., the ratio of packets received to packets sent [31].

Table Ia reveals that the performance of both methods is quite similar, with E2E latency figures being nearly the same ($495.329 \mu s$ vs $495.921 \mu s$), showing a mere $592 ns$ difference. Additionally, both techniques yield the same average number of handovers and PDR, indicating a negligible effect in this scenario. However, the AI-driven approach proves superior in 60% of the simulation runs compared to the distance-based method. Unlike the curvilinear case, as shown in Table Ib, the MPAID algorithm improves performance in 73.33% of the simulation runs. In detail, the average E2E latency is reduced by $4.86 ms$, providing an improvement of 76.90% compared to the distance-based method, and also the mean number of handovers decreases, indicating that our solution effectively avoids unnecessary switches between APs when the mobile MLD STA moves rapidly across their coverage areas. However, MPAID achieves a PDR of 93.1%, while the distance-based method achieves a slightly higher PDR of 94.27%. This suggests that while the MPAID algorithm significantly reduces latency and handovers, there is a marginal trade-off in terms of packet delivery efficiency.

In the more realistic second scenario, which includes interference, Table Ic illustrates that the MPAID algorithm delivers results comparable to those of the distance-based method. The E2E latency values are almost indistinguishable, with the MPAID algorithm recording $618.048 \mu s$ and the distance-based method $618.759 \mu s$, resulting in a minimal difference of roughly $711 ns$. Furthermore, both approaches exhibit the same average number of handovers; however, the MPAID al-

(a) Linear trajectory.

(b) Curvilinear trajectory.

Fig. 5: Comparison of predicted KPIs (in orange) from the LSTM model with those measured using the distance-based approach (in blue) for both linear and curvilinear trajectories. If no values are displayed, it indicates the MLD AP was inactive at that particular timestamp.

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	0.50	0.18	97.43	1
Distance-based Handover	0.50	0.18	97.57	1

(a) First scenario: Linear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	0.62	0.41	94.90	1
Distance-based Handover	0.62	0.41	92.55	1

(c) First scenario: Linear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	1.46	2.75	93.10	1.19
Distance-based Handover	6.32	12.89	94.27	2.44

(b) First scenario: Curvilinear trajectories

	Avg. latency [ms]	Avg. std [ms]	Avg. PDR [%]	Avg. Switch Number
MPAID Handover	2.25	4.14	93.04	1.32
Distance-based Handover	4.04	10.28	91.90	2.11

(d) Second scenario: Curvilinear trajectories

TABLE I: Evaluation of MPAID and distance-based handovers across two scenarios.

Fig. 6: Train and Validation losses of the Classification NN.

gorithm demonstrates a higher PDR compared to the distance-based approach and outperforms the distance-based approach in 56% of the simulation runs. Finally, Table Id highlights a significant improvement in performance achieved by the MPAID algorithm, evidenced by a reduction in the average

Fig. 7: Confusion Matrix showing discrepancies between the ground truth and predicted classified labels.

E2E latency of 1.789 ms. This improvement corresponds to a decrease in the average number of handovers and a higher PDR value. Focusing on curvilinear trajectories, the MPAID algorithm outperforms the distance-based method in 56% of the simulation trials. Hence, even with interference, the proposed MPAID algorithm improves performances.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Our study introduces a new optimized approach for horizontal handovers over Wi-Fi with MLO. Experimental results demonstrate that MPAID reduces both E2E latency and average handover count, outperforming the distance-based baseline in both scenarios considered, where multiple links are involved. In fact, when the MLD STA moves rapidly across the overlapping coverage of the two MLD APs, keeping the link with a single AP proves to be more efficient than executing frequent handovers, even when MLD devices are involved and interference is taken into consideration.

In future work, we could consider adding more interference and a more flexible solution, adaptable to varying network load conditions, numbers of STAs and APs. Moreover, we could use the planned Wi-Fi 8 feature that allows for separate management of each link, thus enabling the STA to maintain simultaneous connections to both APs, switching only when one AP offers much higher performance than the other.

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